

Fig.1

In situ cell mounted to the X-ray diffractometer at BL 2-1, SSRL. Cables for three electrodes are connected as well.

Fig.2

Cross sectional overview of the central parts of the in situ cell. Not all of the parts refer to the same scale.

Fig.3

Disassembled cell after use. Left: PP disk with one O-ring and metal lithium under still wet separator. Right: Steel disk with two O-rings and lithium manganese oxide electrode. Ruler shows size in inches.

Fig.4

[111] Bragg reflection for 4 different X-ray energies, recorded when cell potential was 2.97 eV, the electrode still being LiMn_2O_4 .

Fig.5

Bragg reflections of the original [111] peak for 4 different X-ray energies, recorded when cell potential was 1.54 eV. Splitted peaks indicate phase transition from cubic to tetragonal.

Fig.6

XANES spectra of the LiMn_2O_4 at open cell, and at 1.54 Volt deep discharge. XANES spectrum of Rhodochrosite after [?] is plotted for reference (reproduced from [?] by using QuickTrace [?]).

Fig.7

Evolution of the charge in the cell with increasing charging time (obtained from integration of current through discharge process).

Fig.8

X-ray absorption spectra for EXAFS purposes for LiMn_2O_4 and $\text{Li}_2\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4$
(later refers to point A in Figure 9.

Fig.9

Fourier magnitude for EXAFS data from the cell at three different valence
states for the manganese: 3.50, 3.22, and 3.09.

Fig.10

Two scattering curves of the entire in situ cell at 2 different X-ray energies:
6400 (dotted) and 6545 eV (solid). Scattering curve in center is the weighted
difference $1.365 \cdot I(6400\text{eV}) - I(6545\text{eV})$. Scattering curve at bottom includes
 Q^{-4} -subtraction after Porod. Solid line is from two combined Guinier fits.